

Game Technique and its Classification in the Process of Teaching Students to Volleyball

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Abstract:

The article discusses the work aimed at the development of volleyball sport, methods of selecting volleyball players in groups using regulatory tests and exercises, the acquisition of skills and abilities in the main forms of techniques and tactics of playing volleyball, as well as ways of their preparation.

Keywords: Selection, club, volleyball, sports and selection, selection, regulatory control, wellness and pre-training groups.

INTRODUCTION.

Volleyball differs from other sports in its nature, content and characteristics. The volleyball game is played on a relatively small, square 18x9 meter square, divided equally in the middle. Modern volleyball is extremely rich in different game skills and tactical combinations, and is played at a great intensity and speed. Therefore, the above-mentioned specific characteristics of volleyball require highly developed technical skills from the players. In competitive games, the more extensive and perfectly formed technical skills are in relation to external influences, the greater the chance of winning.

A game technique is a specialized movement or complex of movements performed simultaneously, sequentially and in a specific purposeful order. The technique of the game should be designed for accurate, fast, light, appropriate, low-effort execution of the action.

The term "technique" is a Greek word (tehnus) that is used in a very broad sense and means "art" in the Uzbek language. Starting from 776 BC, every 4 years in the village of Olympus, located at the foot of Mount Olympus in Greece, the participants of the all-Greek holiday competitions held in honor of God Zeus demonstrated their arts (techniques) in 2-wheeled chariot racing, boxing, and

pentathlon. Interestingly, one of the conditions of this competition was that every participant should demonstrate his height, muscle formation and other sports-related qualities before the competition. So, as a result of practicing a certain type of sport, a person's stature, muscles, and all organs of the body are formed, and thus, the improvement of the athlete's technical skills and art is ensured.

Volleyball game technique consists of a set of movement methods necessary to play the game. Movement technique is evaluated by appropriate, effective movement in various situations. The execution of each technique in the game consists of a system of movements that are connected to each other. Movement techniques are dynamic and kinematic properties of movement necessary and sufficient for solving movement tasks in a certain way (certain consistency of forces, coordination between certain parts of the body, etc.).

The main part of the technique is the most important and decisive part of the basic mechanism in a certain movement. Performing the main part of the technique is represented by the expenditure of a large amount of effort in a relatively short period of time.

The details of the technique are secondary features that do not disturb the main mechanism of movement. Technical details are different for different athletes, depending on their morphological and functional capabilities.

When performing technical actions, certain phases of actions are distinguished in terms of time. Usually, three phases of actions can be identified: preparatory, main and final phases.

The importance of the preparatory phase is to create favorable conditions for performing the action in the main phase. These conditions are created by running, jumping, turning movements (blocking, putting the ball in play, attacking). Actions in the main phase are directly focused on solving the main action tasks. From the point of view of biodynamics, the most important thing in this phase is the effective use of driving forces in the appropriate situation and in the appropriate direction.

Movements in the final phase fade or brake sharply in order to maintain the balance of the body. Since volleyball is a very dynamic game, a volleyball player must master various technical methods, be able to choose them depending on the game situation and perform them quickly and accurately. This determines the technical skill of the player.

Signs of high technical skill are represented by:

- accurate and effective implementation of action methods;
- stability of execution of actions in the presence of halal factors (fatigue, negative effects of external conditions);
- choosing response actions depending on the actions of the opponent, reconstructing them and being able to control the parts of the action;
- reliability of execution of methods.

During different periods of volleyball development, the methods, requirements, form, and content of technical movements change and improve. The main reason for the change in technical methods is the change in the rules of the game, the improvement of tactical actions, and the growth of the level of physical fitness of the players. The growth of game dynamics in attack and defense, the increase in the potential of actions, the expansion of the arsenal of combinations in attack and defense also motivates the renewal or reconstruction of technical methods. However, it cannot be said that there are no more effective methods used in game techniques. The functional and physical capabilities of skilled athletes provide an opportunity to introduce and implement new, advanced methods of game technique. Classification of game techniques is to divide them into certain groups and sections based on their form, content, purpose of the used methods, interdependence of actions,

kinematic and dynamic structure of actions. Volleyball techniques are divided into two major sections: offensive and defensive techniques. In turn, the above sections are divided into several groups according to the form and content of technical methods. Each group has its own way of performing technical actions.

The analysis of the literature on the subject allows us to recognize that as a result of the scientific work on the description of modern volleyball and the classification of game techniques, it was noted that the work on the theoretical knowledge of the volleyball sport among schoolchildren playing volleyball is not at a satisfactory level. At this point, it can be observed that as a result of the interviews conducted with high school students, no positive answers were received to the verbal questions about the classification of game techniques.

If we conclude from the above, it can be emphasized that not only volleyball, but also the theoretical aspects of other sports should be paid attention to. Of course, in addition to having sufficient physical, technical and tactical training, it is advisable to engage in theoretical training as well.

Through the above scientific work, in the future we will focus on the general aspects of the sport, which we recognize as modern volleyball, and strengthen the necessary knowledge about the classification of volleyball techniques. At the same time, I hope to make my contribution in preparing them both physically and mentally for the motherland as mature specialists.

Of course, there is a lot of scientific work being carried out in the field of volleyball, and we hope that the professional work carried out by us will further develop the volleyball sport in our independent country, especially in this direction.

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